

Factors of Work Stress as Predictors of Employees Job Satisfaction in Public Organization: The Case of Wegeltena City, Amhara Region, Ethiopia

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ABSTRACT

The main objective of this study was to assess the factors affecting work stress on employees job satisfaction in public organizations of Wegeltena City. An explanatory research design with quantitative approach research was employed. The data was collected from 222 sampled public employees. The samples were selected using stratified random sampling techniques. Questionnaires were used to collect the data. About 219 valid questionnaires was collected. The collected data was analyzed using multiple linear regression. The findings of the study revealed that inflexibility in work hour, management system and work environment have a significant positive effect on employee's job satisfaction, while lack of financial reward have insignificant negative effect and personal issue have insignificant positive effect on employee's job satisfaction. Based on the findings, the study recommends that all concerned bodies should give attention to reduce factor of work stress and should used appropriate measures such as training, counseling and advising. Moreover, the public organization should critically evaluate and potentially revise their management system, work condition, work schedule and rewards that they deliver to workers.

Key words: job satisfaction, lack of financial reward, inflexibility in work hour, personal issue, work environment, and management system.